

DO SPATIAL, SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL PROXIMITY AFFECT CONSUMERS' ETHICAL COFFEE PURCHASING BEHAVIOR? A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN COLOMBIA AND JAPAN

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1. Introduction

Ethical coffee consumption remains constrained by barriers such as the value-action gap, limited traceability [1], certification skepticism and greenwashing [2], and perceived high costs or low availability [3]. Such barriers are shaped by consumers' proximity to production realities, understood as the perceived spatial, social, and psychological closeness to affected actors [4]. This is particularly relevant in global value chains where producer and consumer contexts differ substantially, as in the case of Colombia, a major coffee producer, and Japan, a major importer and consumer with longstanding trade ties.

Currently less attention has been given to the latent characteristics underlying purchasing-behavior factors like pro-environmental behavior, pro-social behavior and perceived behavioral control, especially in cross-cultural comparisons [5]. Accordingly, this study aims to (1) identify key characteristics associated with factors influencing ethical coffee purchasing behavior, (2) compare these influences between Colombia and Japan, and (3) examine how proximity dimensions interact with these factors and characteristics.

1.2. Research Hypotheses

Drawing on prior literature and aligned with the research objectives, this study hypothesizes that environmentally oriented purchasing behaviors increase willingness to purchase ethical coffee, while higher perceived affordability constraints reduce it (H1a–H1b). It further expects cross-country differences, with consumers in Colombia exhibiting greater familiarity with the social and environmental challenges of coffee production, and consumers in Japan perceiving lower affordability constraints (H2a–H2b). Finally, it speculates that higher psychological proximity is positively associated with ethical coffee purchasing, and that proximity operates differently by context, with stronger purchasing characteristics linked to social proximity in Colombia and to psychological proximity in Japan (H3a–H3b).

2. Methodology

2.1. Data Collection

This study employed a cross-sectional comparative survey to examine ethical coffee purchasing behavior among consumers in Colombia and Japan, focusing on the influence of spatial, social, and psychological proximity.

The survey targeted adult coffee consumers who purchase coffee beans or ready-to-drink coffee, assessing

which pro-environmental, pro-social, and perceived behavioral control characteristics are most strongly associated with willingness to purchase (WP) ethically sourced beans and coffee drinks. Levels of knowledge and awareness of ethical coffee were also evaluated. The data was collected via an online, self-administered questionnaire adapted from prior literature and administered in both countries from October 6th – November 6th, 2025.

2.2. Methods of Analysis

As for the first objective of this study, binomial logistic regression (BLR) was applied to identify the key characteristics associated with ethical coffee purchasing factors in Colombia and Japan, regarding willingness to purchase (WP) ethical beans/drinks (1=yes) as dependent variable and taking the items that make up these factors that measure purchasing behavior as categorical Likert explanatory variables. Socioeconomic variables were tested preliminarily but excluded from final models due to unstable income distributions.

Then, stratified BLR per ethical coffee purchasing factor was conducted in order to avoid the quasi-separation risk that comes with implementing a model with a large number of categorical variables, which implies infinite coefficient estimates and standard errors. Thereby, only significant associations ($p < 0.05$) were retained for final multivariable models. In detail, for ethical coffee beans:

$$\begin{aligned} \log\left(\frac{P(WP = 1)}{1 - P(WP = 1)}\right) \\ = \beta_0 + \beta_{1k}Env.Purchase_k + \beta_{2k}Soc.Per.Sacri_k \\ + \beta_{3k}Soc.Close_k + \beta_{4k}BCtrl.Afford_k \end{aligned}$$

For ethical coffee drink:

$$\begin{aligned} \log\left(\frac{P(WP = 1)}{1 - P(WP = 1)}\right) \\ = \beta_0 + \beta_{1k}Env.Purchase_k \\ + \beta_{2k}Soc.Familiar_k + \beta_{3k}Soc.Wellbeing_k \\ + \beta_{4k}Soc.Close_k + \beta_{5k}BCtrl.Afford_k \\ + \beta_{5k}BCtrl.Overall_k \end{aligned}$$

Table 1 shows the description of the explanatory variables. Likewise, since these are Likert-scale variables (1–5) treated as categorical; the lowest category (Ex.:

Env.Purchase1) is used as the reference level in the BLR models.

Table 1 Variables description.

Variable	Description
Env. Purchase	Stated purchase of environmentally-responsible coffee.
Soc.Per.Sacri	Willingness to make personal sacrifices (ex. paying more) to improve farmers' livelihood.
Soc.Close	Effort in being close to farmers by purchasing products from socially responsible brands.
Soc.Familiar	Familiarity with social challenges related to coffee production.
Soc.Wellbeing	Caring about the wellbeing of the farmers.
BCtrl.Afford	Difficulty to afford ethical coffee.
BCtrl.Overall	Overall purchase difficulty of ethical coffee.

As for the second objective, the aim was to compare the purchasing factors and characteristics between Colombia and Japan via subset-specific BLR models mirroring Objective 1's final equations, re-estimating stratified, significant Likert items against WP beans/drinks separately per country.

To complement regression results, Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) was applied to visualize how key purchasing characteristics and WP choices cluster within each country. This way, categories near each other frequently co-occur in respondent profiles; distant ones rarely do.

As for the third objective, the aim was to test proximity dimensions' interactions with key purchasing characteristics from Objectives 1-2. Proximity scales first underwent reliability and structure validation before aggregation into composite scores by calculating the item means per dimension. These scores were included as continuous explanatory variables in BLR models. Subsequently, interaction terms were added to test whether proximity moderates the relationship between purchasing characteristics and WP. In addition, MCA was used to visually explore the joint relationships between proximity dimensions, purchasing characteristics, and WP across countries.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Descriptive statistics of the respondents

The respondents who participated in the survey comprised 343 adult coffee consumers. Table 2 summarizes the main outputs from descriptive statistics.

Coffee consumption was frequent in both countries (typically two to three cups per day), with heavier consumption in Colombia. Purchasing patterns differed: ground coffee dominated in Colombia, while whole-bean coffee was more common in Japan; likewise, supermarkets were the primary purchasing channel. Around 70% of respondents in both countries reported coffee as central to their daily routines.

Perceptions of ethical coffee differed across contexts. Respondents in Japan showed higher conceptual understanding, whereas those in Colombia reported lower

definitional accuracy but higher willingness to purchase ethical coffee and greater trust in certification schemes. Additional information improved recognition of ethically sourced coffee in both countries, particularly for coffee drinks in Japan.

Table 2 Demographics predominant results.

	Japan	Colombia	Total
Location	62.4%	37.6%	100%
Gender			
Female	34.1%	60.5%	44.0%
Male	62.6%	38.8%	53.6%
Age (predominant)			
18-44 y/o	80.9%	62.1%	73.7%
Education (predominant)			
Bachelor	43.9%	8.5%	30.6%
Masters	28.0%	43.4%	33.6%
Employment (predominant)			
Full-time	53.3%	67.4%	58.6%
Student	24.3%	6.2%	17.5%
Income (predominant)			
Upper-middle	42.1%	19.4%	33.5%
High	18.2%	51.2%	30.6%

3.2. Objective 1 results

Given Objective 1 "to identify key characteristics associated with factors influencing ethical coffee purchasing behavior", after assessing internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha and validating the scale structure, the BLR models were estimated; Table 3 shows results:

Table 3 BLR main results, significant characteristics.

Factors	Est.	SE	z-val.	Pr(> z)	OR	95% CI	
Characteristics for WP beans							
EnvPurchase3	1.47	0.45	3.25	0.00	4.36	1.8	10.56
EnvPurchase4	1.79	0.74	2.40	0.02	5.96	1.39	25.61
SocPerSacri5	1.98	0.87	2.27	0.02	7.21	1.31	39.74
BCtrlAfford3	-2.18	1.08	-2.02	0.04	0.11	0.01	0.94
BCtrlAfford4	-2.77	1.09	-2.54	0.01	0.06	0.01	0.53
BCtrlAfford5	-3.17	1.22	-2.60	0.01	0.04	0	0.46
Characteristics for WP coffee drink							
EnvPurchase4	1.67	0.68	2.47	0.01	5.3	1.41	19.93
BCtrlAfford4	-1.36	0.57	-2.39	0.02	0.26	0.08	0.78

The estimated results of Env.Purchase3 and Env.Purchase4 indicate stated purchase of environmentally responsible coffee strongly increased the likelihood of choosing ethical beans, with odds approximately four to six times higher compared to those who never engaged in such purchases. The estimated result of Soc.Per.Sacri5 indicates that the respondents willing to make personal sacrifices to improve coffee farmers' livelihoods exhibited substantially higher odds of selecting ethical beans. Perceived difficulty in affording ethical coffee (BCtrl.Afford4) was negatively associated with WP, with higher affordability difficulty significantly reducing the odds of choosing ethical coffee beans and drinks (OR<1).

For ethical coffee drinks, fewer characteristics were found significant. Stated purchase of environmentally responsible coffee remained a strong positive explanatory variable (Env.Purchase4), increasing the odds of choosing an ethical drink by more than five times. However, perceived affordability (BCtrl.Afford) exerted an even

stronger negative effect in this model, with respondents reporting difficulty affording ethical coffee drinks showing markedly lower odds of selecting the ethical option.

3.3. Objective 2 results

Given Objective 2 “to compare the key characteristics between Colombia and Japan”, country-specific analyses using BLR revealed clear cross-country differences in the factors associated with WP ethical coffee, as well as product-specific patterns.

3.3.1. Results of respondents in Japan

As Table 4 indicates, for the respondents in Japan, the stated purchase of environmentally responsible coffee and a strong willingness to make personal sacrifices to improve farmers’ livelihoods substantially increased the likelihood of choosing ethical beans. In contrast, for ethical coffee drinks in Japan, perceived difficulty in affording ethical options emerged as the only significant explanatory variable, strongly reducing WP, indicating that affordability constraints are particularly salient in out-of-home consumption contexts.

Table 2 BLR Japan results.

Factors	Est.	SE	z-val.	Pr(> z)	OR	95% CI	
Characteristics for WP beans							
EnvPurchase3	1.47	0.5	2.95	0.00	4.36	1.64	11.62
SocPerSacri5	2.17	0.97	2.25	0.03	8.73	1.32	57.86
Characteristics for WP coffee drink							
BCtrlAfford4	-2.56	1.25	-2.05	0.04	0.08	0.01	0.9

3.3.2. Results of respondents in Colombia

The results of the respondents in Colombia imply that there are no characteristics significantly predicted WP ethical coffee beans. This suggests that the included pro-environmental, pro-social, and perceived behavioral control factors do not systematically differentiate between consumers willing and unwilling to choose ethical beans. In contrast, WP ethical coffee drinks in Colombia was positively associated with familiarity with the social challenges of coffee production, although the 95% CI of 1.43-148.18 showed considerable uncertainty, indicating heterogeneity within the subsample.

3.3.3. WP patterns in Colombia and Japan by MCA

MCA was used to explore relational patterns among characteristics and WP across countries and products. For the Japan subsample, the MCA results aligned with the BLR findings, it revealed more structured and polarized profiles among consumers, particularly for ethical bean purchases, while Colombian consumers displayed more diffuse and less clearly differentiated patterns, aligned with regression results as well. For coffee drinks, MCA results in both countries highlighted the central role of perceived affordability and familiarity with production challenges, supporting the regression-based findings. Taken together, these results indicate that ethical coffee purchasing drivers differ not only between producing and importing countries, but also between product types, with stronger attitudinal structuring observed in Japan and more heterogeneous behavioral patterns in Colombia.

3.4. Objective 3 results

Given Objective 3 “to examine how proximity dimensions interact with the factors and their characteristics”, composite scores for spatial, social, and psychological proximity were constructed. Reliability and factor analyses supported treating the three dimensions as internally consistent and conceptually distinct constructs, enabling their inclusion as explanatory variables in BLR models.

For the overall sample proximity effects differed by product type. Psychological proximity was positively associated with WP ethical coffee beans, indicating that greater understanding of coffee farmers’ challenges increases the likelihood of ethical choices for at-home consumption. In contrast, social proximity was the only dimension significantly associated with WP ethical coffee drinks, suggesting that feelings of social connection and identification with farmers are more influential in out-of-home consumption contexts. Table 5 shows these results:

Table 5 BLR results.

Proximity	Est.	SE	z-val.	Pr(> z)	OR	95% CI	
Significant proximity for WP beans							
PsychProx	0.8124	0.2328	3.49	0.0005	2.253	1.43	3.56
Significant proximity for WP coffee drink							
SocialProx	0.5157	0.2165	2.381	0.0173	1.675	1.1	2.56

3.4.1. Country-specific results

In Japan, psychological proximity significantly predicted WP ethical coffee beans, while none of the proximity dimensions were significant for ethical coffee drinks, indicating that proximity plays a limited role in drink-related decisions. Regarding Colombia, social proximity emerged as the strongest explanatory variable for both ethical coffee beans and drinks, highlighting the importance of perceived social connection in a producing country context. Additionally, on a categorical-based approach, Table 6 shows BLR results for stratified proximity items:

Table 6 BLR significant proximity items per country

Prox. item	Est.	SE	z-val.	Pr(> z)	OR	95% CI	
Significant proximity items for WP beans [JP]							
PsychUnderstand3	1.591	0.636	2.501	0.012	4.908	1.41	17.08
Significant proximity items for WP coffee drink [JP]							
PhysicalSeenMedia2	1.182	0.512	2.31	0.021	3.261	1.2	8.89
PhysicalSeenMedia3	1.943	0.653	2.973	0.003	6.978	1.94	25.12
PhysicalSeenMedia4	1.242	0.444	2.796	0.005	3.461	1.45	8.27
PsocDifConnected5	2.586	1.203	2.151	0.032	13.277	1.26	140.18
Significant proximity items for WP coffee drink [COL]							
PsocDifConnected2	2.521	1.17	2.154	0.031	12.441	1.26	123.3
PsocDifConnected4	3.171	1.041	3.046	0.002	23.827	3.1	183.31

This item-level analyses further showed that understanding farmers’ daily challenges (PsychUnderstand3) and exposure to media depicting coffee production conditions (PhysicalSeenMedia2-4) were consistently associated with higher WP ethical products. Estimates regarding feeling connection with the farmers despite having different living conditions (PsocDifConnected2-5) although significant, displayed substantial uncertainty due to limited observations in

extreme response categories.

3.4.2. Interaction effects

Interaction models testing whether proximity moderated the effects of purchasing-behavior characteristics found no statistically significant interaction effects. This indicates that proximity exerts an independent influence on ethical purchasing decisions rather than amplifying or weakening the effects of pro-environmental or pro-social behaviors or perceived behavioral control.

3.4.3 Proximity, factors and WP by MCA

MCA supported the previous findings by revealing clearer and more structured proximity behavior associations among consumers in Japan and more heterogeneous, dispersed patterns among consumers in Colombia. Overall, the results confirm that proximity dimensions matter for ethical consumption, but their influence varies by country and product type, with psychological proximity more salient for ethical coffee beans (Fig.1) and social proximity more influential for ethical coffee drinks (Fig.2).

Figure 1 MCA for WP beans with significant purchase-behavior characteristics, proximity items and location.

Figure 2 MCA for WP drink with significant purchase-behavior characteristics, proximity items and location.

3.5. Discussion

3.5.1 Objective 1: Key purchasing characteristics.

Pro-environmental behavior, particularly stated purchases of environmentally responsible coffee, emerged as the strongest ethical coffee driver across beans/drinks (OR 4.4-5.9), confirming environment-focused routines narrow value-action gaps better than attitudes alone [6]. Pro-social behavior, specifically the willingness to make personal sacrifices for farmers' livelihood, showed large beans effects (OR≈7) but limited drinks influence, likely due to weaker producer traceability in ready-to-drink

formats. Finally, affordability consistently reduced WP (OR 0.2-0.3, 70-96% lower odds), reinforcing price as the primary barrier for habitual products [6].

3.5.2. Objective 2: Colombia vs Japan contrasts.

Stated environmentally friendly purchase dominated both contexts but structured WP more clearly in Colombia (MCA: high categories near WP=1) versus Japan's diffuse patterns. Pro-social effects appeared Japan specifically for beans (OR=8.73, Soc.Per.Sacri), while MCA showed fragmentation overall. Affordability constrained Japan consumer drink purchases most (92% lower odds at high difficulty), but Colombia's high-income profiles muted this barrier, reflecting country-specific respondent demographics.

3.5.3. Objective 3: Proximity effects.

Psychological proximity drove WP beans (OR=2.25), social proximity drinks (OR=1.67), with country patterns aligning. The psychological-related strongest item in Japan was empathy, whereas social-related item in Colombia was shared identity despite lifestyle differences. No significant interactions emerged; proximity contributed additively alongside purchasing traits [7]. MCA confirmed Colombia clusters near WP=1/low affordability barriers/high psychological and social proximity; Japan shows accurate knowledge but weaker psychological and social proximity/low environmental purchase, explaining hesitation despite awareness.

4. Conclusion

This study analyzed how spatial, social, and psychological proximity shape ethical coffee purchasing through consumer characteristics across producer Colombia and importer Japan. Results show that pro-environmental routines, such as purchasing environmentally responsible coffee, the willingness to make pro-social sacrifices, and affordability constraints are the primary determinants of willingness to purchase ethical coffee. Likewise, proximity dimensions contribute additively rather than interactively, specifically, cross-country contrasts indicate stronger affordability constraints and actual knowledge in Japan and a greater role of social and psychological proximity in Colombia, highlighting context- and product-specific drivers of ethical consumption.

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